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INSILICO ACTIVITY PREDICTION OF DIAZEPINES DERIVATIVES

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ABSTRACT

The term psychosis is very broad and can mean anything from relatively normal aberrant experiences to the complex and catatonic expressions of schizophrenia and bipolar type-1 disorder¹. Many targets for the treatment of psychosis are available namely NMDA receptor antagonists, Ketamine and MK-801, peptide deformylase, Acetylcholinesterase, G protein-coupled receptors, glutamate synthase (NADPH). The Protein-Ligand interactions plays a significant role in structural steroid hormones glutamate synthase (NADPH) Acetylcholinesterase, G protein-coupled receptors, transforming based drug designing. In our Present research work we have chosen glutamate synthase² (NADPH) and Acetylcholinesterase³ as targets to screen our proposed chemical structures for anti-psychotropic activity. The molecules were docked to the above said targets and the energy values obtained are as follows using the docking software. Depending on the energy values we have chosen the best two drug analogs they are Compound 3e {-9.4}, Compound 3k {-10.0}. We tried to improve the binding efficiency and steric compatibility. Several modifications were made to the probable functional groups which are interacting with receptor molecules. Analogs of this drug molecule were prepared using ACD-chem.-sketch and docking. The modified drugs was sketched using chem.-sketch were found to be better than the conventional drugs available.

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INTRODUCTION

1H-1,3-diazepine

Molecular Formula: C₅H₆N₂

Formula Weight: 94.11454

Diazepines and its Derivatives^{4,5}:

1) Novel 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulfonyl 1,4-diazepine derivatives, which were synthesized, characterized and tested as anti-schistosomal agents *in vitro*. showed the highest schistosomicidal activity.

2) 1-H-1,5-benzodiazepines and 1,2-disubstituted benzimidazoles in good yields by the condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine with several ketones and aldehydes, respectively.

CHALCONES⁶ :

Chalcones, considered to be the precursor of flavonoids and iso flavonoids, are abundant in edible plants. They consist of open-chain flavonoids in which the two aromatic rings are joined by a three-carbon α , β -unsaturated carbonyl system. Studies revealed that compounds with a chalcone-based structure have anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, anti-fungal, and anti-tumor activities. These activities are largely attributed due to the α , β -unsaturated ketone moiety. Introduction of various substituents into the two aryl rings is also a subject of interest because it leads to useful structure-activity relationship (SAR). Equimolar quantities of a substituted acetophenone with substituted aldehydes in the presence of aqueous alcoholic alkali. In the Claisen-Schmidt reaction, the concentration of alkali used, usually ranges between 10 and 60 %. The reaction is carried out at about 50 °C for 12-15 hours. Under these conditions, the Cannizzaro reaction also takes place and thereby decreases the yield of the desired product. To avoid the disproportionate of aldehyde in the above reaction, the use of benzylidene-diacetate in place of aldehyde has been recommended.

Michael Adducts diazepine chalcones:

Among all heterocyclic compounds, Michael Adducts diazepine chalcones are one of the most important heterocyclic structures exhibiting remarkable pharmacological activities because it is an essential constituent of all cells⁷. Michael Adducts diazepine chalcones is a six-membered heterocyclic ring containing two nitrogen atoms at position 1 and 14 of the 5 and 6 membered rings.

Mechanism

Michael Adducts Reaction:

Experimental work:**MATERIALS AND METHODS:**

Tools and Materials Used: - For our present study we used bioinformatics tools, biological database like PDB (protein data bank) and software like ACD/chem. sketch, organic chemistry portal and molecule docking. ACD/chem. sketch is the powerful all-purpose chemical drawing and graphics package from ACD/labs developed to help chemist quickly and easily draw molecules, reactions, and schematic diagrams, calculate chemical properties and design professional reports and presentations. ACD chem. sketch can convert "SMILES" notations to structure and vice versa⁸. PDB (protein data bank) is the single worldwide archive of structural data of biological macromolecules, established in Brookhaven national laboratories (BNL) in 1971. It contains structural information of the macromolecules determined by X-ray crystallographic, NMR methods ect. Docking allows the scientist to virtually screen a database of compounds and predict the strongest binders based on various scoring functions. It explores ways in which two molecules, such as drugs and an enzyme or receptor fit together and docks to each other well, like pieces of a three-dimensional zigzag puzzle. The molecules binding to a receptor, inhibit its function, and thus act as drug. The collection of drug analogs and receptor complexes was identified via docking and their relative stabilities were evaluated using molecular dynamics and their binding affinities, using free energy simulations. All the parameters used for molecule docking are selected by default.

Table 1: Substitutions of Michael adducts pyridyl derivatives and Smiles File.

S.No	SUBSTITUTIONS	SMILE FILES
1	4-Cl	<chem>Clc1ccc(cc1)C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>
2	3-Cl	<chem>Clc1cccc(c1)C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>
3	2-Cl	<chem>Clc1ccccc1C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>
4	4-NO ₂	<chem>O=N(=O)c1ccc(cc1)C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>
5	3-NO ₂	<chem>O=N(=O)c1cccc(c1)C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>
6	2-NO ₂	<chem>O=N(=O)c1ccccc1C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>
7	4-F	<chem>Fc1ccc(cc1)C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>
8	3-F	<chem>Fc1cccc(c1)C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>
9	2-F	<chem>Fc1ccccc1C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>
10	4-SO ₃ H	<chem>O=S(=O)(O)c1ccc(cc1)C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>
11	3-SO ₃ H	<chem>O=S(=O)(O)c1cccc(c1)C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>
12	2-SO ₃ H	<chem>O=S(=O)(O)c1ccccc1C1CC(=NC1C)C1=CC=NC=CN1</chem>

Figure 1: Structure of Targets.

Acetylcholinesterase
PDB ID: 1DX4
Organism: *Drosophila melanogaster*

Glutamate Synthase(NADPH)
PDB ID: 1EA0
Organism: *Azospirillum Brasilense*

Table2: Substitutions and their codes:

S.No	CODE	SUBSTITUTIONS
1	3a	4-Cl
2	3b	3-Cl
3	3c	2-Cl
4	3d	4-NO ₂
5	3e	3-NO ₂
6	3f	2-NO ₂
7	3g	4-F
8	3h	3-F
9	3i	2-F
10	3j	4-SO ₃ H
11	3k	3-SO ₃ H
12	3l	2-SO ₃ H

Table3: Structures of Ligands:

RESULT

Out of 12 proposed chemical structures only best four structures were selected and their energy values are tabulated below. Which were docked with the mentioned targets.

Table 4: Drug like properties predicted from MOLSOFT, MOLINSPIRATION Property calculator the following are the properties of Michael Adducts diazepine derivatives.

S.No	CODE	Mi logp	TPSA	n atoms	MW	n ON	n OHNH	n violations	nrotb	volume	Druglikeliness
1	3a	3.70	41.05	20	285.78	3	1	0	2	256.67	-0.07
2	3b	3.67	41.05	20	285.78	3	1	0	2	256.67	-0.11
3	3c	3.18	41.05	20	285.78	3	1	0	2	256.67	-0.04
4	3d	2.98	86.87	22	296.33	6	1	0	3	266.47	-0.68
5	3e	2.96	86.87	22	296.33	6	1	0	3	266.47	-0.49
6	3f	2.46	86.87	22	296.33	6	1	0	3	266.47	-0.72
7	3g	3.18	41.05	20	269.32	3	1	0	2	248.07	-0.17
8	3h	3.16	41.05	20	269.32	3	1	0	2	248.07	-0.21
9	3i	2.66	41.05	20	269.32	3	1	0	2	248.07	-0.33
10	3j	0.01	95.42	23	269.32	3	1	0	2	282.58	-0.07
11	3k	-0.01	95.42	23	269.32	3	1	0	2	282.58	-0.56
12	3l	-0.51	95.42	23	269.32	3	1	0	2	282.58	-1.06

Table 5: Docking score predicted from Mcule the following are the properties of Michael Adducts diazepine derivatives.

S.No	CODE	SUBSTITUTIONS	Druglikeliness	Docking score	
				Glutamate Synthase(1EA0)	Acetylcholinesterase (1DX4)
1	3a	4-Cl	-0.07	-8.0	-9.4
2	3b	3-Cl	-0.11	-7.9	-9.2
3	3c	2-Cl	-0.04	-8.0	-8.8
4	3d	4-NO ₂	-0.68	-9.6	-9.3
5	3e	3-NO ₂	-0.49	-9.4	-9.7
6	3f	2-NO ₂	-0.72	-8.7	-9.2
7	3g	4-F	-0.17	-8.6	-9.6
8	3h	3-F	-0.21	-8.4	-9.6
9	3i	2-F	-0.33	-8.4	-8.8
10	3j	4-SO ₃ H	-0.07	-8.0	-9.4
11	3k	3-SO ₃ H	-0.56	-8.8	-10.0
12	3l	2-SO ₃ H	-1.06	-8.7	-9.1

Ligand: 3d

Table 6:

S.No	CODE	SUBSTITUTIONS
1	3a	4-Cl
2	3b	3-Cl
3	3c	2-Cl
4	3d	4-NO ₂
5	3e	3-NO ₂
6	3f	2-NO ₂
7	3g	4-F
8	3h	3-F
9	3i	2-F
10	3j	4-SO ₃ H
11	3k	3-SO ₃ H
12	3l	2-SO ₃ H

Table 7:

S.No	CODE	SUBSTITUTIONS	Druglikeliness	Docking score	
				Glutamate Synthase(1EA0)	Acetylcholinesterase (1DX4)
1	3a	4-Cl	-0.07	-8.0	-9.4
2	3b	3-Cl	-0.11	-7.9	-9.2
3	3c	2-Cl	-0.04	-8.0	-8.8
4	3d	4-NO ₂	-0.68	-9.6	-9.3
5	3e	3-NO ₂	-0.49	-9.4	-9.7
6	3f	2-NO ₂	-0.72	-8.7	-9.2
7	3g	4-F	-0.17	-8.6	-9.6
8	3h	3-F	-0.21	-8.4	-9.6
9	3i	2-F	-0.33	-8.4	-8.8
10	3j	4-SO ₃ H	-0.07	-8.0	-9.4
11	3k	3-SO ₃ H	-0.56	-8.8	-10.0
12	3l	2-SO ₃ H	-1.06	-8.7	-9.1

Ligand: 3e.

Table 8:

S.No	CODE	SUBSTITUTIONS
1	3a	4-Cl
2	3b	3-Cl
3	3c	2-Cl
4	3d	4-NO ₂
5	3e	3-NO ₂
6	3f	2-NO ₂
7	3g	4-F
8	3h	3-F
9	3i	2-F
10	3j	4-SO ₃ H
11	3k	3-SO ₃ H
12	3l	2-SO ₃ H

Table 9:

S.No	CODE	SUBSTITUTIONS	Druglikeliness	Docking score	
				Glutamate Synthase(1EA0)	Acetylcholinesterase (1DX4)
1	3a	4-Cl	-0.07	-8.0	-9.4
2	3b	3-Cl	-0.11	-7.9	-9.2
3	3c	2-Cl	-0.04	-8.0	-8.8
4	3d	4-NO ₂	-0.68	-9.6	-9.3
5	3e	3-NO ₂	-0.49	-9.4	-9.7
6	3f	2-NO ₂	-0.72	-8.7	-9.2
7	3g	4-F	-0.17	-8.6	-9.6
8	3h	3-F	-0.21	-8.4	-9.6
9	3i	2-F	-0.33	-8.4	-8.8
10	3j	4-SO ₃ H	-0.07	-8.0	-9.4
11	3k	3-SO ₃ H	-0.56	-8.8	-10.0
12	3l	2-SO ₃ H	-1.06	-8.7	-9.1

Ligand:3k.

Table 10:

S.No	CODE	SUBSTITUTIONS
1	3a	4-Cl
2	3b	3-Cl
3	3c	2-Cl
4	3d	4-NO ₂
5	3e	3-NO ₂
6	3f	2-NO ₂
7	3g	4-F
8	3h	3-F
9	3i	2-F
10	3j	4-SO ₃ H
11	3k	3-SO ₃ H
12	3l	2-SO ₃ H

Table 11:

S.No	CODE	SUBSTITUTIONS	Druglikeliness	Docking score	
				Glutamate Synthase(1EA0)	Acetylcholinesterase (1DX4)
1	3a	4-Cl	-0.07	-8.0	-9.4
2	3b	3-Cl	-0.11	-7.9	-9.2
3	3c	2-Cl	-0.04	-8.0	-8.8
4	3d	4-NO ₂	-0.68	-9.6	-9.3
5	3e	3-NO ₂	-0.49	-9.4	-9.7
6	3f	2-NO ₂	-0.72	-8.7	-9.2
7	3g	4-F	-0.17	-8.6	-9.6
8	3h	3-F	-0.21	-8.4	-9.6
9	3i	2-F	-0.33	-8.4	-8.8
10	3j	4-SO ₃ H	-0.07	-8.0	-9.4
11	3k	3-SO ₃ H	-0.56	-8.8	-10.0
12	3l	2-SO ₃ H	-1.06	-8.7	-9.1

Ligand:3l

Table 12:

S.No	CODE	SUBSTITUTIONS
1	3a	4-Cl
2	3b	3-Cl
3	3c	2-Cl
4	3d	4-NO ₂
5	3e	3-NO ₂
6	3f	2-NO ₂
7	3g	4-F
8	3h	3-F
9	3i	2-F
10	3j	4-SO ₃ H
11	3k	3-SO ₃ H
12	3l	2-SO ₃ H

Table 13:

S.No	CODE	SUBSTITUTIONS	Druglikeness	Docking score	
				Glutamate Synthase(1EA0)	Acetylcholinesterase (1DX4)
1	3a	4-Cl	-0.07	-8.0	-9.4
2	3b	3-Cl	-0.11	-7.9	-9.2
3	3c	2-Cl	-0.04	-8.0	-8.8
4	3d	4-NO ₂	-0.68	-9.6	-9.3
5	3e	3-NO ₂	-0.49	-9.4	-9.7
6	3f	2-NO ₂	-0.72	-8.7	-9.2
7	3g	4-F	-0.17	-8.6	-9.6
8	3h	3-F	-0.21	-8.4	-9.6
9	3i	2-F	-0.33	-8.4	-8.8
10	3j	4-SO ₃ H	-0.07	-8.0	-9.4
11	3k	3-SO ₃ H	-0.56	-8.8	-10.0
12	3l	2-SO ₃ H	-1.06	-8.7	-9.1

CONCLUSION

Based on the literature it has been shown clearly that the compounds 3d,3e,3k,3l have been used to target (a) & (b) receptors where the compound 3e and 3k on docking with the target (a) & (b) produced an energy value of [-9.4] and [-10.0] respectively. Drug likeliness performed in the software of molsoft. Where the drug analog using the "SMILES" notation which are generated by the chem.-sketch. By using the molinspiration online software, the drug analogs are undergone for their molecular properties like mlogp, natoms, nON, nOHNH, nViolations, nroth, Volume, molecular weight, TPSA and Drug likeliness where some of the drug analogs have been shown the good drug like liness.

Docking pose of proposed chemical structures:

Figure 2: Docking pose of 3d with the target 1EA0.

Figure 3: Docking pose of 3e with the target 1EA0.

Figure 4: Docking pose of 3k with the target 1DX4.

Figure 5: Docking pose of 3l with the target 1DX4.

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